
CHANGING ROLE OF COLLEGE LIBRARIES IN ICT ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract:

Today era is the era of Information technology. The 21st century is known as knowledge society. In the 21st century new trends in technology are developed. That's why there is huge change occurred in social scenario. There is a lot of changes happened in social, economical, educational & political views. ICT has changed the nature of College libraries. A variety of terms such as hybrid, digital and virtual library are used to refer to the academic library. The pace of change brought about by new information technologies has a key effect on the way people live.

ICT enabled learning would help to grasp the opportunities offered by ICT to prepare for learning in the 21st century that embraces digital technologies for better learning, for better assessment of learning outcomes and achievement for better teaching and for better social inclusion.

Libraries are changing in terms of their collection, facilities and services owing to constant changing scenario of information due to ICT (Information Communication Technology) applications and information seeking behavior of the users. The Library apart from providing traditional library services in a computerized environment act as Learning Resource Centre.

This paper is a literature review on changing role of College Libraries in ICT's Environment.

Keywords: *ICT, College Libraries, Library Professional, Librarian etc.*

Introduction:

The 21 century is the age of Information technology. The 21st century is known as knowledge society. Today ICT has almost covered the whole world into global village. ICT have revolution ways of working transformed the economy, had an irreversible impact on the way peoples live and have shaped a new information society. The information system challenges the education system. The necessity of universal access to

information services is tated in several declarations, which stress the need to broaden access and use of ICT declaration that everyone everywhere should be enabled to participate in the global information society.

Libraries have to adapt to growth of information and communication technology in recent years. Today people use the internet as primary source of information. In the term of administration running a library is now much simpler than

before. Use of ICT in Various libraries for collection, Storing, processing and disseminate the information in the electronic form. With the development of information and communication technology the library environment has shifted from the traditional library to hybrid library, to automated library, to electronic library to digital library, to virtual library or web library and presently it is being adapted to library 2.0 are used synonymously to represent the same concept, the terms are used differently by different authors. However the central theme of the terminologies remains focused on digital content of the document.

Definition of ICT:

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2010) defines ICT as the forms of technology that are used to transmit, process, store, create, display, share or exchange information by electronic means. This broad definition of ICT includes such technologies as radio, television, video, DVD, telephone (both fixed line and mobile phones), satellite systems, and computer and network hardware and software, as well as the equipment and services associated with these technologies, such as videoconferencing, e-mail and blogs. The list of technologies that ICT encompasses is been updated daily as new technologies are invented or designed. Thus we can say ICT is a generic term that refers to technologies, which are being used for collecting, storing, editing and communicating of information in various forms from one user to another.

Benefits of ICT in Libraries:

Benefits of ICT in libraries as stated by Ashikuzzaman (2014) include:

- Provision of speedy and easy access to information.
- Provision of remote and round the clock access to users.
- Provision of access to unlimited information from different sources.
- ICT enable easier, faster, cheaper and more effective library operations.
- ICT helps to manage information overload as information retrieval is made easier in computerized systems.
- Computerization helps the library to save space and reduce paper.
- Remote access is enabled through networked systems.

Changing role of College Libraries in ICT Environment:

Change is the need of the development of the human lives or any other organization or institutions. The change is necessary for development of the people's attitude. The main goal of the library and information center is to fulfill the users need and their satisfaction. The result of any change the user gets maximum benefit. Some of the changes in library and information centers with the application of ICT.

Change in Library Activities:

- Automation of library by using various software in housekeeping operations.
- Collection development in digital and electronic form such as E-Books, E-Journals, E-Encyclopedia etc. Acquisition of content access and organization of contents.

- Website management, electronic document delivery, digitization.

Applications of Modern Technologies in College Libraries:

With the existence of ICT so many modern library services are came into existence, many technologies making influence on the traditional libraries. The modern technologies are applicable to College Libraries are as follows:-

1. Library Automation:

Library Automation is a process where is using computer-based system to do house-keeping operations. e.g. acquisition, circulation, classification, cataloguing, serial control etc. The ICT made possible for automation in libraries. For Library automation there are open source and commercial software's are available in the society i.e., Koha, New-Gen-lib, Evergreen, as well as many commercial software SOUL, Libsys, SLIM21, etc.

1.1 Need of Library Automation:

Academic Library needs to redesign the process to achieve quality of e-facility. So this ICT environment library needs to adopt new techniques to create healthy atmosphere for library e-facilities & services.

- To improve the existing services
- Different approaches and needs/demands of user
- To obtain increased operational efficiencies
- To improve the access the resources on other networks and systems, including the web
- To enable their participation in resources-sharing library networks
- To improve the management of their physical and financial resources

- To use the services of the existing staff effectively.
- Some Limitations of library (Manpower, time & Space)
- Availability of information in various formats (Print/Non-print, graphical, audio-visual)

2. RFID Technology:

RFID (Radiofrequency Identification) is the latest technology to be used in the library for book identification for self-checkout and for sorting and conveying of library books and also for theft detection. The RFID management system in libraries can be implemented in following ways.

- Library Security System
- Library Circulation System
- Self-Check in & Check outs
- Smart & quick Inventor

3. Cloud Computing:

Many libraries traditionally manage servers with huge volume of data & sometimes critical problems regarding with their management that is lack of expertise & the cost involvement in acquisition & maintenance of require software and Hardware.

For example- in the special or research libraries they hold the data in digitally converted of rare or heritage documents, but sometimes there is risk of data security & universal access. So the libraries can apply cloud computing to data integrity, upgrade & maintenance, intellectual property management, backup, etc.

It facilitates reduced operation costs of IT resources, increases operation efficiency, and extends distributed access through virtualized environment. By adopting this change, libraries can increase reliability, declined costs due to economics of scale and other production factors.

4. Digital Library: Institutional Repositories (IR):

A Institutional Repositories is a type of content management system that both holds the core intellectual assets of a university or college, and enables them to be used to support a variety of business process as defined in the institution's information strategy.

e.g. In a content management system holds resources for a particular course or department website. A repository can hold a comprehensive set of core assets that can then be used in a flexible way for different purposes, such as teaching an undergraduate course via a virtual learning environment (VLE) underpinning a website, or collating a university's research outputs across a particular subject area or period of time.

Need for Changing Role of Librarian with ICT Environment:

Information and communication technology has become essential part of 21st century's libraries. ICT has made drastic change in the field of libraries, the libraries has transformed from traditional libraries to digital libraries or hybrid libraries. Therefore the librarians must create technological environment to make sense of a multiplicity of digital collections and resources. They must identify strategies to provide access to wide range of networks & information resources. For this purpose they need new skills to manage and create many information sources and services. The competencies & skills form the basis for the continued survival and growth of professional in the new information technology age. So in the fast changing environment, the library professional must possess multi skills, multi-tasking abilities and competent in specialized

area of work.

Conclusion:

Open access supported by information technology has become a public movement globally and this movement has provided new challenges as well as opportunities for the librarians. The libraries are implementing ICT based library services and librarians managing digital library and hybrid library, institutional repositories publishing maintaining open access E-journals, E-Books and developing web portal. Open access provides a new paradigm for libraries and librarians. It provides opportunities for library professionals to deliver qualitative and quantitative content in to the users.

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